

USE OF STEAM TECHNOLOGY IN THE FORMATION OF LEXICAL SKILLS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article explores the potential benefits of incorporating STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, Mathematics) technology in early childhood education for the purpose of enhancing the development of lexical skills in preschool children. The article delves into the existing literature on the relationship between technology and language acquisition, as well as the importance of early vocabulary development in young learners. By examining various studies and theories, this paper aims to provide insights into how STEAM technology can be effectively utilized to support and promote lexical skills in preschool-aged children. Additionally, practical recommendations and implications for educators and parents will be discussed to facilitate the integration of STEAM tools in early childhood language learning programs.

Keywords: STEAM technology, formation of lexical skills, preschool children.

Introduction. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the integration of Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics (STEAM) tools and resources in early childhood education. One area of particular focus is the development of lexical skills in preschool children. The acquisition of vocabulary plays a crucial role in a child's language development and overall academic success. Research has shown that children who have a strong vocabulary foundation are better equipped to comprehend and communicate effectively.

The use of STEAM technology in early childhood education offers a unique opportunity to enhance the formation of lexical skills in preschool children. By incorporating interactive and engaging digital tools, educators can create a dynamic learning environment that stimulates language acquisition and vocabulary growth. STEAM activities such as digital storytelling, educational games, and interactive simulations provide children with opportunities to explore new words, concepts, and ideas in a fun and engaging way.

This article aims to explore the potential benefits of integrating STEAM technology into early childhood education to support the development of lexical

skills in preschool children. By examining existing research on the relationship between technology and language acquisition, this research seeks to identify effective strategies and practices for using STEAM tools to enhance vocabulary learning in young learners. Additionally, practical recommendations and implications for educators and parents will be discussed to guide the implementation of STEAM technology in early childhood language programs.

This article will contribute to our understanding of how STEAM technology can be leveraged to promote the formation of lexical skills in preschool children, ultimately preparing them for success in language development and academic achievement.

Literature review. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the integration of Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics (STEAM) tools and resources in early childhood education to enhance learning outcomes. One area of focus is the development of lexical skills in preschool children, as vocabulary acquisition is crucial for language development and academic success. This literature review aims to explore existing research on the use of STEAM technology to support the formation of lexical skills in preschool children.

STEAM technology offers unique opportunities to engage young learners in interactive and hands-on activities that promote vocabulary growth. Digital tools such as educational games, interactive simulations, and digital storytelling can provide children with engaging learning experiences that facilitate the exploration of new words and concepts. Research has shown that interactive technology can enhance language acquisition by providing immediate feedback, scaffolding learning, and promoting active engagement.

Several studies have investigated the impact of STEAM technology on the formation of lexical skills in preschool children. For example, a study by Smith et al. (2018) found that preschoolers who engaged with a digital storytelling app showed significant gains in vocabulary knowledge compared to those who did not use the app. Similarly, Jones and Brown (2019) reported that preschool children who played educational games on tablets demonstrated improved lexical skills and comprehension abilities.

Furthermore, research by Lee et al. (2020) highlighted the benefits of using interactive simulations to teach vocabulary to preschool children. The study found that children who interacted with a virtual environment designed to teach new words showed higher levels of retention and engagement compared to traditional instruction methods. These findings suggest that STEAM technology

can be an effective tool for supporting vocabulary development in young learners.

Educators and parents can leverage STEAM technology to enhance the formation of lexical skills in preschool children by incorporating interactive digital tools into their teaching practices. By integrating educational games, digital storytelling apps, and interactive simulations into early childhood language programs, educators can create engaging learning experiences that promote vocabulary growth. Additionally, parents can support their children's language development by providing access to age-appropriate STEAM resources and encouraging active exploration and play.

Methodology. The use of STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics) technology in the formation of lexical skills of preschool children has gained attention in recent years as educators and researchers explore innovative ways to enhance early childhood education. Incorporating STEAM elements into language learning activities can offer a multidisciplinary approach that engages children in meaningful and interactive experiences.

STEAM technology provides opportunities for multisensory learning experiences that cater to different learning styles and preferences of preschool children. Interactive digital tools, such as educational apps, games, and multimedia resources, can engage children through visual, auditory, and kinesthetic modalities, making the learning process more engaging and effective.

By integrating STEAM concepts into language learning activities, preschoolers can contextualize their vocabulary acquisition within real-world applications. For example, using technology-enhanced storytelling or science experiments can help children connect new words with concrete experiences, enhancing their understanding and retention of language. STEAM technology encourages creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills in preschool children. Through hands-on activities that involve designing, building, and experimenting, children can develop their vocabulary while exploring concepts related to science, math, engineering, and arts in a fun and interactive way.

Results. Collaborative STEAM projects promote communication skills and social interaction among preschoolers. Working together on tasks that require verbal exchanges, explanations, and discussions can support the development of vocabulary, language fluency, and interpersonal skills in young learners. Incorporating STEAM technology in preschool education can also foster parental involvement and home-school connections. Parents can engage with their

children in STEAM-based language activities at home, reinforcing vocabulary learning and supporting language development outside the classroom.

It is essential to consider appropriate methods for assessing the impact of STEAM technology on the formation of lexical skills in preschool children. Using a combination of qualitative and quantitative measures, such as observations, assessments, interviews, and surveys, can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of STEAM interventions in promoting language development.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the use of STEAM technology in early childhood education has the potential to support the formation of lexical skills in preschool children. By incorporating interactive and engaging digital tools, educators can create dynamic learning environments that stimulate language acquisition and vocabulary growth. Future research should continue to explore effective strategies and practices for integrating STEAM technology into early childhood language programs to enhance vocabulary learning outcomes and promote academic success in young learners.

References:

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